

Deliverable D-PhD16-3.2
PhD 16 - Codes4strain

Responsible Partner: Institut Pasteur

GENERAL INFORMATION

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D-PHD16-3.2

cgLINcodes algorithm defined and implemented on full dataset

We used the pilot *K. pneumoniae* dataset (**D-PhD16-2.1**) to develop a LIN codes algorithm applied to cgMLST profiles, which we call cgLINcodes. We have implemented the LIN code attribution algorithm using the Python programming language. The developed cgLINcoding software tool takes as input a file of allelic profiles and a set of thresholds, defining a LIN code scheme. Then, the tool returns two files:

- LIN DataBase: a file containing the LIN codes associated with each allelic profile, allowing to create new LIN codes from future profiles;
- Genome LIN code list (genome names and their LIN code)

We have implemented the cgLINcode attribution algorithm using the Python programming language and made the script available publicly (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/LINcoding>).

The developed cgLINcoding software tool takes as input a file of allelic profiles and a set of thresholds, defining a cgLINcode scheme. Then, the tool returns two files:

- cgLIN DataBase: a file containing the cgLINcodes associated with each allelic profile, allowing to create new cgLINcodes from future profiles;
- Genome cgLINcode list (genome names and their cgLINcode)

These cgLINcodes are composed of a set of p -positions, each corresponding to a threshold of similarity between genomes. These similarity thresholds are sorted in ascending order (*i.e.*, $s_p < s_{p+1}$), the first positions of the code (on the left side) thus corresponding to low levels of similarity. Following the initial proposal, the codes are assigned as follows: (step 1) The code is initialized with the first strain being assigned the value "0" at all positions; (step 2) The encoding rule for a new genome i is based on the closest genome j already encoded as follows, from the similarity $s_{ij} \in]s_{p-1}; s_p]$:

- identical to code j up to and including position $p - 1$.
- for the position p : maximum value observed at this position (among the subset of codes sharing the same prefix at the position $p - 1$) incremented by 1.
- "0" to all downstream positions, from $p + 1$ included.

For each genome to be encoded, step 2 is repeated. This encoding system conveys phylogenetic information, as two genomes with identical prefixes in their respective cgLINcodes can be understood as being similar, to an extent determined by the length of their common prefix. Isolates having cgMLST profiles with 100% identity (no mismatch at loci called in both genomes) will have exactly the same cgLINcode.

In the course of our experiments and literature searches, we noticed that this method has a significant problem of dependency on the order of entry of isolates. In other words, according to their encoding order, the same set of allelic profiles can lead to LIN codes resulting in categorizations by different prefixes. We therefore sought to minimize this problem by defining an optimal input order. As a result, we found that the one generated by minimum spanning tree algorithm generates partitions that are comparable to single linkage clustering.

To implement the cgLINcodes approach to the full dataset of the *K. pneumoniae* species, an important issue was the definition of the set a thresholds. We aimed to define thresholds taking into account the phylogenetic structure of the species, and to maximize its usefulness in population biology and epidemiology. The distribution of pairwise similarity values among 7060 available genomes was used to determine discontinuities in the genetic structure of the species. The codes must also be intuitive enough to be largely adopted by epidemiologists. We are finalizing a nomenclature system comprising 10 thresholds based on our current understanding of the phylogenetic structure of the species.

The link to access the algorithm is: <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/LINcoding>

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All the files used by the LINcoding script as well as the files generated by it are located at the following
address: https://bigsdbs.web.pasteur.fr/klebsiella_INSDC/LINcodes/ < file >

Where < file > should be any of the following:

- klebs.N7060.T1.L10-638.txt: cgMLST profiles
- klebs.N7060.d: pairwise matrix
- LIN_klebs.N7060.txt: genome LIN code list of 7060 Kp
- database.klebs.N7060.lin: LIN DataBase of Kp